

1 **Factors Influencing Monoclonal Antibody Pharmacokinetics Across Varying Immune Perturbations**

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13 Keywords: Monoclonal Antibody, Pharmacokinetics, Immune Knockout, Mathematical Modeling

14 **Graphical Abstract**

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21 **Abstract**

22 The development of continuous-release devices or injectables for the long-term delivery of biologics is of
23 great interest, especially monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) that require frequent, high-dose injections.
24 Preclinical testing of these technologies in murine models is necessary for clinical translation; however,
25 xenogeneic responses to the mAb and foreign body responses to the implants or injectables can confound
26 results. Immune system knockout (KO) models that affect immune cells are often used in these experiments,
27 but the effects of KO models on mAb pharmacokinetics (PK) are not well characterized. Here, we
28 investigated the PK profile of the human mAb 3BNC117 after intravenous, subcutaneous, and
29 intraperitoneal injections in four mouse strains: BL6, BCD, RAG2, and NSG mice. Noncompartmental
30 analysis was used to quantify differences in PK between each mouse strain. Strikingly, both BL6 and NSG
31 mice exhibited significantly higher mAb clearance compared to the other two strains. To better understand
32 these differences, we developed a minimal physiologically based PK model of mAb PK incorporating FcγR
33 interaction in the peripheral tissue and the formation of anti-drug antibodies. The estimated model
34 parameters demonstrate that the rapid clearance in the BL6 and NSG strains can be explained by the
35 formation of anti-drug antibodies and increased FcγR abundance in peripheral tissues, respectively. We then
36 used simple allometric scaling relationships to assess which strains were reasonably predictive of human
37 mAb PK. The scaled parameters obtained from BCD and RAG2 mice led to reasonably accurate human
38 predicted PK, whereas the parameters obtained from NSG and BL6 mice did not. These results emphasize
39 that the mechanistic differences influencing NSG and BL6 PK must be considered when assessing the
40 translatability of data.

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45 **Introduction**

46 Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) are a highly versatile biotherapeutic modality with the potential to treat
47 many different patient indications. In 2023, 20% of newly approved drugs were mAbs, primarily due to
48 their high target specificity, diverse range of functionality, and serum stability [1,2]. Engineering of the
49 mAb variable region (Fab) allows for a broad range of target proteins to be selected, and the effect of target
50 binding can be manipulated by engineering of the constant region (Fc). Thus, mAbs are capable of treating
51 a wide range of diseases [3,4]. There are many approved mAbs for the treatment of cancer and autoimmune
52 disease [5], and others are in clinical development for the treatment of other indications such as HIV [6],
53 Malaria [7], COVID-19 [8], bacterial sepsis [9], and even Alzheimer's disease [10]. However, mAbs are
54 typically administered as intravenous (i.v.) or subcutaneous (s.c.) injections, requiring large and frequent
55 doses for long-term efficacy. For this reason, technologies for the sustained and controlled release of mAbs
56 are of great interest due to their ability to maintain more durable and consistent therapeutic concentrations
57 over the course of treatment [4,11,12]. These technologies often take the form of implantable devices [13–
58 15] or injectable hydrogels [16–18] that, when injected into peripheral tissue, continuously release mAb
59 such that exposure is maintained for extended periods of time.

60 Any new continuous-release platform needs to be tested in appropriate preclinical models to verify the
61 durability of the technology and pharmacokinetic (PK) profile of the released mAb. Murine models are a
62 vital step in this characterization, especially for implantable devices, where it is difficult to predict how an
63 implant and its released substance will perform in the complex *in vivo* environment. For example, host
64 responses such as the foreign body response (FBR) against the implant and the anti-drug antibody (ADA)
65 response against the released substance can make interpreting experimental data difficult [19–21]. Several
66 murine models are often needed to systematically isolate facets of implanted device performance. For
67 example, if one wishes to test the fibrotic axis of FBR on the profile of released mAb in the absence of
68 ADA response, a mouse model such as the B6.129S2-Ighmtm1Cgn/J strain, which lacks functional B cells,
69 would prevent the development of an ADA response [22]. In other studies, such as those evaluating implant

70 biocompatibility, a general-purpose healthy model such as the C57BL6 strain is useful [23]. Utilizing
71 murine models with varying levels of immunodeficiency caused by genetic perturbations, often by gene
72 knockout (KO models), is a valuable method to characterize continuous-release device performance.
73 However, caution is needed to avoid making incorrect assumptions when only one KO model is used.

74 The Fc region of mAbs binds to a variety of Fc receptors on immune cells, and some subclasses of Fc
75 receptors are known to affect mAb PK. The most prominent example is neonatal Fc receptor (FcRn) binding
76 and recycling, which leads to reduced mAb clearance and longer half-lives [24,25]. Because immune
77 system KO leads to changes in the immune system's composition, KO models can exhibit differential PK
78 partly due to changes in Fc receptor abundance. In the context of severely immunocompromised mouse
79 strains, evidence in the literature suggests that the distinct mAb PK profile observed in such strains results
80 from FcγR binding in peripheral tissues [26–28]. Unlike FcRn, FcγR binding can occur at extracellular pH
81 and is hypothesized to cause internalization and degradation [29]. This phenomenon has been linked to the
82 efficacy of anti-CD20 mAbs for the treatment of B-cell malignancies [30], but the specific impact on mAb
83 PK is not well characterized. Additionally, mice with fully functional immune systems are known to elicit
84 ADA [31], further complicating the relationship between immune KO and mAb PK.

85 Here, we investigate the effects of immune system KO on mAb PK following bolus intravenous (i.v.),
86 subcutaneous (s.c.), and intraperitoneal (i.p.) injections. To this end, we evaluated the PK of 3BNC117
87 following bolus i.v., s.c., and i.p. injections in four mouse strains with varying levels of immune KO.
88 3BNC117 is a fully human mAb that binds to the GP120 spike protein of HIV and has been shown in
89 clinical trials to neutralize HIV in infected patients [32,33]. A minimal physiologically based PK (mPBPK)
90 model incorporating FcγR binding and degradation with mouse weight and strain as covariates accurately
91 represents the collected data and is used to quantify the PK differences across mouse strains. The model is
92 then combined with simple allometric scaling to assess which mouse strains exhibit mAb PK relevant for
93 clinical translation.

94 **Methods**

95 *Reagents*

96 The purified 3BNC117 mAb protein used in the in vivo studies described was provided by the Duke
97 Human Vaccine Institute Protein Production Facility and facilitated by the Collaboration for AIDS
98 Vaccine Discovery and the Gates Foundation. This mAb was originally isolated from an HIV-infected
99 donor and shown to broadly neutralize across HIV clades with high affinity [34]. As such, it is a fully
100 human IgG1 mAb, whose sequence was determined and used to produce recombinant mAb for this study.
101 The total Human IgG enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit used for the quantification of
102 3BNC117 serum levels was purchased from Abcam (Cat No: ab195215). All other reagents and
103 consumables used in the study were obtained from various commercial sources.

104 *Animals*

105 C57BL/6NCrl (BL6) mice (8 weeks old, female) were purchased from Charles River Laboratories strain
106 Code #027. B6.129S2-Ighmtm1Cgn/J (BCD) mice JAX Strain #002288, B6.Cg-Rag2tm1.1Cgn/J (RAG2)
107 mice JAX Strain #008449, and NOD.CgPrkdcscid Il2rgtm1Wjl/SzJ (NSG) mice JAX Strain #005557 (8
108 weeks old, female) were purchased from Jackson Laboratories.

109 *Animal Experiments*

110 Animal experiments in this study were performed in accordance with the Guidelines for the Care and Use
111 of Laboratory Animals at Rice University, which is accredited by the Association for Assessment and
112 Accreditation of Laboratory Animal Care (AAALAC) International.

113 *Evaluation of 3BNC117 PK in Mice*

114 The PK of 3BNC117 in murine serum was evaluated by administering bolus i.v., s.c., and i.p. injections at
115 a fixed dose of 56 µg. The drug solution consisted of purified 3BNC117 antibody in sterile Dulbecco's
116 phosphate-buffered saline and was administered at a volume of 100 µL. Animals were excluded from
117 subsequent blood collection and analysis if i.v., s.c., or i.p. administration was incorrectly performed,
118 leading to some variability in sample size between experimental groups. Blood was collected from the
119 saphenous vein without anesthesia. Blood samples were taken at 1 hour, 4 hours, 1 day, 3 days, 7 days, and

120 ~weekly thereafter until blood concentrations fell below the limit of quantification (LOQ) of the ELISA
121 (2.3 ng/mL due to dilution) or 100 days was reached. Blood samples were allowed to coagulate for 1 hour
122 at room temperature, then centrifuged at 3,500xG for 10 minutes to allow the collection of serum. The
123 collected serum was stored at -80 C until analysis via ELISA.

124 *Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for quantification of 3BNC117 in serum samples*

125 Total Human IgG ELISA kits obtained from Abcam were utilized, and the manufacturer's protocol was
126 followed. Samples were diluted into the dynamic range of the assay with the supplied sample diluent.
127 Following the addition of the sample to supplied 96-well plates, the addition of capture and detector
128 antibody, washing, 15-minute incubation with tetramethylbenzidine (TMB), and addition of the stop
129 solution, the absorbance was measured at OD450 nm using an infinite M200 Pro plate reader (Tecan).
130 Concentrations were then calculated using standard curves.

131 *ELISA assay for the detection of 3BNC117-binding mouse IgG (ADA) in serum samples*

132 96-well MaxiSorp plates (Thermo Scientific Cat: 439454) were coated with 50 µL of 10 µg/mL 3BNC117
133 in DPBS at 4°C overnight. The plate was then washed 3x with Wash Buffer PT (from Abcam kit ab212169).
134 The plate was then blocked using Bio-Rad Everyblot blocking buffer following the manufacturer's
135 instructions (Cat: 12010020). The plate was then washed 3x with Wash Buffer PT. To generate a standard
136 curve for quantification, a mouse anti-human IgG1 (Thermo ref A10630 Lot 2978770) was serially diluted
137 in sample diluent (from Abcam kit ab212169), and 100 µL of sample was added to the plate. Stored serum
138 samples (-80°C) were thawed from chosen timepoints from the I.V. portion of the strain comparison study
139 shown in Figure 1 to run this assay. Then 100 µL of serum samples diluted 1:200 in sample diluent were
140 added to the plate, and it was covered with an adhesive plate cover and incubated at 37 °C on a rocker plate
141 for 1.5 hours. The plate was washed 3x, and 100 µL of Goat anti-Mouse IgG HRP conjugated antibody
142 (Invitrogen ref 31430) was added to all wells at a 10,000x dilution per manufacturer's suggestion. The plate
143 was incubated and covered at 37 °C for 1 hour on a rocker plate. The plate was washed 3x, and 100 µL of
144 TMB development solution (from Abcam kit ab212169) was added. The plate was incubated at room

145 temperature for 30 minutes, covered by aluminum foil, on a shaker plate at 400 rpm. 100 μ L of Stop solution
146 (from Abcam kit ab212169) was added to all wells, and the absorbance was measured at OD450 nm using
147 an infinite M200 Pro plate reader (Tecan). Concentrations were then calculated using the standard curve.

148 *Noncompartmental Analysis*

149 Noncompartmental analysis (NCA) was performed using the ‘NonCompart’ and ‘ncar’ packages in R [35].
150 Maximum observed concentration (C_{max}), the area under the concentration v. time curve (AUC), clearance
151 (CL), terminal half-life ($t_{1/2}$), bioavailability (F) and steady-state volume of distribution (V_{ss}) were
152 calculated for each mouse. Bioavailability was calculated based on the mean calculated AUC_{Inf} value for
153 each strain according to:

$$F = \frac{AUC_{Inf}^{e.v.}}{\overline{AUC}_{Inf}^{i.v.}} \quad (1)$$

154

155 Where $AUC_{Inf}^{e.v.}$ is the area under the curve calculated after extravascular (s.c. or i.p.) administration and
156 $\overline{AUC}_{Inf}^{i.v.}$ is the average calculated area under the curve for the same strain of mouse following i.v.
157 administration. Values for each NCA parameter were compared based on mouse strain.

158 *Statistical Analysis*

159 NCA parameters were compared across experimental groups. Data was plotted as mean \pm standard deviation
160 in bar charts. Statistical differences between groups were assessed using two-way ANOVA for those data
161 sets comparing administration routes and strain, while one-way ANOVA was utilized for strain differences
162 alone as well as within doses for the dose escalation study. Each mouse strain was compared to the BL6
163 strain by post hoc multiple comparisons tests using Dunnett’s test within administration routes if applicable.
164 Statistical analysis for outlier exclusion was performed on data points that were visually aberrant using
165 ROUT outlier detection with $Q = 1\%$ within administration routes, treating each time point as a group.
166 These statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism software (version 10.3.1, for Windows,
167 GraphPad Software, Boston, Massachusetts USA, www.graphpad.com). Statistical significance was

168 defined as $p < 0.05$ and when graphing * $p < 0.0332$, ** $p < 0.0021$, *** $p < 0.0002$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Statistical
 169 testing of ADA results was done following the same procedure comparing groups within time point and
 170 adding additional comparisons across Day 1, 14, and 30 for the BL6 group.

171 *Minimal Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Model of Bolus mAb Injection*

172 An mPBPK model of bolus mAb injection, absorption, distribution, and elimination was developed based
 173 on several models in the literature [36–40]. The model consists of six total compartments: the central/blood
 174 compartment (B), the peripheral tissue compartment (T), the peripheral lymphatic compartment (P), the
 175 central lymphatic compartment (L), the subcutaneous dosing compartment (S), and the intraperitoneal
 176 dosing compartment (I). Because mAb clearance is primarily mediated through cellular uptake and
 177 lysosomal degradation [41–43], we assume that clearance can occur in any model compartment.
 178 Additionally, due to the large molecular weight of 3BNC117, we assume that transport only occurs via
 179 convective transport in the direction of lymph flow [44]. The concentration of mAb in each compartment
 180 is described by the following ordinary differential equations:

$$\frac{dC_B}{dt} = \frac{j_{BL}}{V_B} C_L - \frac{j_{TB}}{V_B} C_B - k_{CL}^B(t) C_B \quad (2)$$

181

$$\frac{dC_S}{dt} = -\frac{j_{PS}}{V_S} C_S - k_{CL}^S C_S \quad (3)$$

182

$$\frac{dC_I}{dt} = -\frac{j_{PI}}{V_I} C_I - k_{CL}^I C_I \quad (4)$$

183

$$\frac{dC_T}{dt} = \frac{j_{TB}}{V_T} C_B - \frac{j_{PT}}{V_T} C_T^f - k_{CL}^L C_T^f - k_{int} C_T^b \quad (5)$$

184

$$\frac{dC_P}{dt} = \frac{j_{PS}}{V_P} C_S + \frac{j_{PI}}{V_P} C_I + \frac{j_{PT}}{V_P} C_T^f - \frac{j_{LP}}{V_P} C_P - k_{CL}^L C_P \quad (6)$$

185

$$\frac{dC_L}{dt} = \frac{j_{LP}}{V_L} C_P - \frac{j_{BL}}{V_L} C_L - k_{CL}^L C_L \quad (7)$$

186 Here, C_x is the total (bound and unbound) concentration of mAb in compartment x , C_T^f is the unbound
 187 concentration of mAb in the peripheral tissue compartment, C_T^b is the bound concentration of mAb in the
 188 peripheral tissue compartment, V_x is the volume of compartment x , j_{yx} is the rate of mAb-carrying fluid
 189 flow from compartment x to compartment y , k_{CL}^x is the first order clearance rate constant from compartment
 190 x , and k_{int} is the first order internalization and degradation rate constant for FcγR:mAb complex. The
 191 concentrations of total and free mAb in the peripheral tissue compartment were calculated using an
 192 equilibrium assumption [45] such that the concentration of free mAb is given by:

$$C_T^f = 0.5 \left(C_T - R - K_D + \sqrt{(C_T - R - K_D)^2 + 4C_T K_D} \right) \quad (8)$$

193 Where R is the concentration of total FcγR in the peripheral tissue compartment and K_D is the dissociation
 194 constant for mAb:FcγR binding. The concentration of bound mAb in the peripheral tissue compartment is
 195 determined by mass conservation according to:

$$C_T^b = C_T - C_T^f \quad (9)$$

196

197 Importantly, we assume that mAb bound to FcγR is immobilized and, therefore, transport out of the
 198 peripheral tissue compartment depends on the free concentration of mAb. Species concentrations are in
 199 units of pmol/mL and are converted to mass for plotting using a molecular weight of 146.25 kDa based on
 200 the amino acid sequence of 3BNC117. Bolus injection of mAb was represented by setting the initial
 201 concentration of mAb in the corresponding compartment according to:

$$C_{x,0} = \frac{D}{V_x} \quad (10)$$

202 where D is the dose administered (ng). Mouse strain and starting weight were included in our model as
 203 covariates. Weight influenced volumes and all elimination rate constants according to:

$$k_{CL}^x = k_{CL,0}^x \left(\frac{BW}{BW_{median}} \right)^{-0.09} \quad (11)$$

204

$$V_B = V_{B,0} \left(\frac{BW}{BW_{median}} \right) \quad (12)$$

205 where BW is the mouse weight and BW_{median} is the median weight of all mice. Allometric scaling
 206 exponents exhibiting good performance for mAbs were taken from the literature [46,47]. Mouse strain
 207 influenced the time-dependence of clearance from the central compartment and the efficiency of mAb
 208 reabsorption into the blood following distribution into peripheral tissue. Time-dependent clearance was
 209 represented using an empirical relationship similar to other models in the literature [37,38] according to:

$$k_{CL}^B(t) = k_{CL}^B(0) \exp \left\{ \frac{T_{max} t^g}{T50^g + t^g} \right\} \quad (13)$$

210 Where T_{max} determines the maximum log fold change, $T50$ is the time at which clearance reaches 50% of
 211 its maximum log fold change, g is a hill coefficient, and $k_{CL}^B(0)$ is the value of the clearance rate constant
 212 at time zero. BL6 mice were given a time-dependent increase in elimination (positive T_{max}), and RAG2
 213 and BCD mice were given a time-dependent decrease in elimination (negative T_{max}). Time-dependent
 214 clearance was not required to fit NSG mouse data.

215 *Parameter Estimation with Nonlinear Mixed Effects Modeling*

216 In total, the developed model has 35 parameters (**Table S1**), with 8 fixed parameters based on literature
 217 values or best approximations, 25 parameters estimated via fitting to data, and 2 parameters based on
 218 measured mouse body weights. For model fitting, measured values below the LOQ but above the limit of
 219 detection (LOD) were included for parameter estimation as described in the literature [48]. Model

220 parameters and inter-individual variability (IIV) were estimated using nonlinear mixed effects modeling
 221 with the nlmixr package in R [49–51] using the FOCEI estimation method, log-normally distributed
 222 parameters, and proportional and additive error. Random effect parameters were selected by first estimating
 223 model parameters with only random effect parameters, and down-selecting based on calculated shrinkage
 224 values and analysis of Empirical Bayes Estimates (EBEs) for the presence of strain-dependence.

225 **Results**

226 **Table 1: Description of the effects of immune KO in each mouse strain investigated.**

Functional Immune Cell Population	BL6 mice C57BL/6NCrl	BCD mice B6.129S2- Ighmtm1Cgn/J	RAG2 mice B6.Cg- Rag2tm1.1Cgn/J	NSG mice NOD.CgPrkdcscid Il2rgtm1Wjl/SzJ
Monocyte	+	+	+	+
Macrophage	+	+	+	-
Basophil	+	+	+	+
T-Cell	+	+	-	-
B-Cell	+	-	-	-
Neutrophil	+	+	+	+
Dendritic Cell	+	+	+	-
Eosinophil	+	+	+	+
Natural Killer Cell	+	+	+	-

227

228 *Immune System Perturbations Significantly Alter Monoclonal Antibody Pharmacokinetics*

229 To interrogate the effect of immune KO on 3BNC117 PK, purified 3BNC117 was administered to four
 230 strains of mice: C57BL6 (BL6), B6.129S2-Ighmtm1Cgn/J (BCD), B6.Cg-Rag2tm1.1Cgn/J (RAG2), and
 231 NOD.CgPrkdcscid Il2rgtm1Wjl/SzJ (NSG). BL6 mice are a fully immune-competent, general-purpose

232 mouse model, while the other strains
 233 contain targeted contain genetic
 234 mutations that cause immune cell
 235 perturbations: BCD mice lack mature B
 236 cells, RAG2 mice lack mature T and B
 237 cells, and NSG mice are extremely
 238 immunodeficient, lacking functional
 239 macrophages, dendritic cells, hemolytic
 240 complement system, T cells, B cells and
 241 natural killer cells (Table 1) [22,52–55].
 242 Initially, bolus 56.0 μg i.v., s.c., and i.p.
 243 injections were administered to each

244 strain (Figure 1A-C). Serum was collected at 1 hour, 4 hours, 24 hours, 3 days, 7 days, and approximately
 245 weekly thereafter until the study date completion or until the concentration fell below the LOQ of the assay.
 246 The concentration of mAb in serum samples was determined using a human IgG ELISA (Abcam 195215).
 247 Comparison of the 3BNC117 concentration vs. time curves following 3BNC117 dosing in each mouse
 248 demonstrates that immune KO has varying but significant effects on 3BNC117 PK. In BL6 mice, 3BNC117
 249 follows a typical mAb PK profile consisting of rapid distribution and slow elimination phases [41,43] until
 250 roughly one week, when mAb elimination rapidly increases. 3BNC117 PK in RAG2 and BCD mice,
 251 however, does not exhibit this rapid increase in elimination and is similar in both strains. In stark contrast
 252 to all other strains, NSG mice exhibited a rapid decrease in serum mAb concentrations immediately after
 253 dosing and fell below the LOQ of the assay after roughly one week.

254 To determine whether the time-dependent increase in clearance in BL6 mice was due to a time-dependent
 255 ADA phenomenon or a saturable phenomenon such as target-mediated drug disposition (TMDD), we
 256 administered additional i.v. injections of 6.22, 18.67, and 168.4 μg to determine if the observed trends were

257 dose-dependent (**Figure 1D**). Collected concentration vs. time measurements demonstrate that the increase
258 in clearance was not dose-dependent and occurred between 10-15 days following injection at all dose levels.
259 These trends illustrate that the increase in clearance is due to a time-dependent, dose-independent
260 phenomenon characteristic of ADA rather than TMDD. Furthermore, we utilized an ELISA with 3BNC117
261 bound to the plate to detect the presence of mouse IgG that binds to 3BNC117 (ADA) in the serum samples

262 taken from each mouse. Significant levels of ADA were only detectable in serum taken from BL6 mice and
 263 increased in a time-dependent manner (Figure 2).

264 To quantify the observed differences in mAb PK between strains, we next compared NCA parameters
265 following 56 μg injections in each mouse strain, including C_{max} , AUC , bioavailability (F), CL , and $t_{1/2}$
266 (**Figure 3, Supplementary Figure S1, Supplementary Data 1**). Following i.v. administration at this dose
267 level, C_{max} values for all four mouse strains were similar, but s.c. and i.p. administration led to significantly
268 different values across strains. Furthermore, C_{max} following i.p. administration was higher than after s.c.
269 administration in all cases (**Figure 3A**). Despite similar C_{max} values, calculated AUC values varied across
270 mouse strains, with NSG mice exhibiting significantly reduced values compared to BL6 mice. RAG2 and
271 BCD mice exhibited significantly increased AUC compared to other strains (**Figure 3B**). Similarly,
272 bioavailability (F) values varied across mouse strains and were improved following i.p. injections compared
273 to s.c. injections. (**Figure 3C**). Bioavailability values greater than 100% were observed in some RAG2 and
274 BCD mice following i.p. administration, which has been reported for other mAbs in rodent and primate
275 models [56,57]. NSG and BL6 mice also exhibited much higher clearance rates and shorter half-lives than
276 RAG2 and BCD mice (**Figure 3D-E**).

277 To identify the possible mechanisms leading to the unexpectedly high clearance observed in NSG mice, we
278 conducted a brief literature search. Multiple identified studies suggest that the rapid clearance in NSG mice
279 results from increased $Fc\gamma R$ abundance and binding in peripheral tissues. First, Sharma and colleagues
280 demonstrated that mAbs exhibit differential biodistribution compared to less-severely immunodeficient
281 strains and accumulate in the spleen, bone marrow, and liver. By blocking Fc -receptor binding, mAb
282 biodistribution in these mice returns to normal [26]. The works of Oldham et al. [27] and Li et al. [28]
283 further support these findings by demonstrating that mAb binding to multiple $Fc\gamma R$ s is responsible for the
284 rapid clearance of mAb in severely immunodeficient mice and that ablation of this binding also restores PK
285 profiles to normal. Furthermore, Li et al. demonstrate that NSG mice have a higher abundance of $Fc\gamma R$ -
286 expressing cells in the bone marrow, spleen, and liver [28]. The absence of endogenous IgG in NSG mice
287 can also lead to a higher abundance of free $Fc\gamma R$ in these tissues [26]. Based on these findings, we

288 hypothesize that the abnormal PK we observed in NSG mice is a result of increased abundance of free FcγR
 289 in peripheral tissues, leading to mAb sequestration and inhibited lymphatic reabsorption to the blood.

290 *PK Data is Accurately Represented by a Minimal Physiologically Based PK Model*

291 To determine if the proposed mechanisms can account for the trends observed in data and to quantify the
 292 potential effects of these mechanisms, we developed an mPBPK model representing mAb dosing via bolus
 293 i.v., s.c., or i.p. injection, distribution into peripheral tissues, lymphatic transport from peripheral tissues to
 294 circulation, and clearance from each compartment based on similar models in the literature [36–39] (**Figure**
 295 **4, Equations 2-13**). We represented the formation of ADA in our model empirically with a time-dependent
 296 increase in the clearance rate constant from the central compartment in BL6 mice. Furthermore, RAG2 and
 297 BCD PK profiles were best captured with a decrease in the clearance rate constant at long times, but the
 298 underlying mechanism is unclear. To incorporate our proposed mechanism that increased FcγR expression
 299 in the peripheral tissue of NSG mice, which leads to accumulation in peripheral tissue and limited reuptake
 300 into the blood, we added a simple binding and internalization reaction scheme in the peripheral tissue
 301 compartment. The concentration of FcγR in the peripheral tissue compartment was assumed to be strain-
 302 dependent.

303 Model parameters were estimated with nonlinear mixed effects modeling with mouse strain and body
304 weight as covariates. Initial parameter estimates were determined with the naïve pooled approach [58], and
305 parameters were estimated using the FOCEI estimation method in the nlmixr package in R. Parameter
306 estimation results in model predictions that are in good agreement with experimental data (**Figure 5,**
307 **Supplementary Figure S2**). The best-performing model contained both mixed and random effect
308 parameters, with j_{TB} , j_{PT} , j_{PS} , j_{PI} , $k_{CL,0}^B$, T_{max}^{BL6} , $T50^{BL6}$, and $V_{B,0}$ having inter-individual variability (IIV)
309 (**Table 2, Supplementary Figure S3**). Specifically, the mechanisms incorporated in our model successfully
310 capture the time-dependent increase observed in BL6 mice at all doses tested (**Figure 5A-B**) and the rapid
311 initial decrease in serum mAb observed in NSG mice (**Figure 5C**). In the absence of these aspects, the PK
312 profiles of 3BNC117 are well-captured in both RAG2 and BCD mice (**Figure 5D-E**).

313 **Table 2: Estimated fixed and random effect parameters.** Values are reported to two significant digits.
314 BSV: Between subject variability (%)

Fixed Effect Parameters		
Parameter	Estimated Value (Units)	
$k_{CL,0}^S$	0.79 (1/day)	
$k_{CL,0}^I$	0.93 (1/day)	
$k_{CL,0}^L$	2.7e-4 (1/day)	
g^{BL6}	2.3 (unitless)	
T_{max}^{RAG2}	2.4 (unitless)	
$T50^{RAG2}$	25 (days)	
g^{RAG2}	2.5 (unitless)	
T_{max}^{BCD}	1.5 (unitless)	
$T50^{BCD}$	72 (days)	
g^{BCD}	1.5 (unitless)	
k_{int}	0.194(1/day)	
R^{BL6}	2.0e3 (pmol/mL)	
R^{NSG}	6.5e6 (pmol/mL)	
R^{RAG2}	4.3e3 (pmol/mL)	
R^{BCD}	1.7e3 (pmol/mL)	
σ^{prop}	0.28 (unitless)	
σ^{add}	0.014 (pmol/mL)	
Random Effect Parameters		
Parameter	Estimated Value (Units)	BSV
j_{TB}	1.5 (mL/day)	23%
j_{PT}	0.076 (mL/day)	23%
j_{PS}	0.19 (mL/day)	34%
j_{PI}	11 (mL/day)	28%

$k_{CL,0}^B$	0.18 (1/day)	24%
T_{max}^{BL6}	3.2 (unitless)	25%
$T50^{BL6}$	5.8 (days)	27%
$V_{B,0}$	1.3 (mL)	30%

Figure 5: Model fitness to experimental data. A-B) Fitness to BL6 data. C) Fitness to NSG data. D) Fitness to RAG2 data. E) Fitness to BCD data. Red points: experimental data. Solid black lines: model predictions. Dashed black line: Lower limit of quantification. RLMSE: Root log-mean squared error

316 To further validate our mPBPK model, we sought to validate that model predictions were qualitatively
317 consistent with observations in the literature. The first major observation we tested was that the increased
318 clearance observed in severely immunocompromised mouse strains coincides with increased FcγR
319 expression and accumulation of mAb in peripheral tissues 148 hours after bolus i.v. administration [26–28].
320 We simulated our model using the parameters estimated for each mouse and plotted the mean and raw 95%
321 interval central compartment concentration (**Figure 6A**) and peripheral tissue mass (**Figure 6B**) grouped
322 by mouse strain. In line with reported trends, model simulations predict that the increased expression of
323 FcγR in the peripheral tissue of NSG mice leads to sequestration of mAb in peripheral tissue and a
324 corresponding reduction in serum concentration. The next observation we sought to replicate is that the
325 mitigation of FcγR binding restores the abnormal PK and biodistribution observed in immunodeficient
326 mouse strains [26,28]. To this end, we simulated our model using each individual NSG mouse's parameters
327 with varying levels of FcγR binding affinity. Plotting the average predicted serum concentration and
328 peripheral tissue mass grouped by FcγR binding affinity reveals that our model predictions are consistent
329 with the reported trend that weak FcγR binding restores mAb PK in severely immunocompromised mouse
330 strains (**Figure 6C-D**). Overall, the ability of our model to replicate these trends supports its biological
331 relevance.

332 We next analyzed the estimated parameters and quantified how specific processes in our model change
 333 based on each mouse strain. First, the time dependence of clearance in BL6, RAG2, and BCD mice was
 334 characterized by calculating the fold change in the clearance rate constant over time based on the estimated
 335 parameters for each mouse. In BL6 mice, the estimated parameters indicate that the effects of ADA vary
 336 between mice. The clearance rate constant starts increasing around 3-5 days following dosing and reaches

337 a 20x increase after 30 days on average (**Figure S4A**). Conversely, the change in clearance occurs much
338 later in both RAG2 and BCD mice. The clearance rate constant is predicted to reach a maximum decrease
339 of 90% after ~75 days in RAG2 mice, whereas in BCD mice, the change is more gradual, reaching a
340 decrease of over 50% after 100 days (**Figure S4B**). Furthermore, we used the estimated parameter values
341 for each mouse to quantify the fraction of antibody absorbed into the blood from the s.c. and i.p.
342 compartments after dosing (**Figure S4C-D, Supplementary Text**). Absorption of 3BNC117f from the s.c.
343 was calculated to be impaired in NSG mice compared to other strains (**Figure S4C**), but i.p. absorption
344 fractions were estimated to be similar (**Figure S4D**).

346 To assess the clinical translatability of 3BNC117 in each mouse strain tested, we applied simple allometric
 347 scaling relationships [31,46,47] to estimate human model parameters from each mouse strain. Parameters
 348 pertaining to compartment volumes were transformed using an allometric scaling exponent of 1, lymph

349 flow rates of 0.73, and rate constants of -0.09. The exponent for compartment volumes was selected based
350 on standard practice [31,47]. The exponents for lymph flow rates and clearance rates were selected based
351 on the findings of Zhao and colleagues, who demonstrated with a similar mPBPK model that these
352 exponents allowed for accurate prediction of human mAb PK by scaling parameters obtained from mice
353 [46]. We assumed that T_{max} and g in our empirical form of time-dependent clearance did not scale with
354 body weight, but T_{50} scales with an exponent of 0.09. We simulated 30 mg/kg i.v. injections of 3BNC117
355 in human patients using these estimated parameters (**Figure 7A-B**) and compared the resulting PK profiles
356 to clinical trial data in HIV-negative patients [32]. Clinical trial data was extracted graphically using
357 GraphGrabber2.0.2 (Quintessa). Notably, human predictions using NSG- or BL6-scaled parameters deviate
358 significantly from the expected human profile. Human predictions based on RAG2- or BCD-scaled
359 parameters exhibit both the rapid distribution and slow-elimination phases consistent with human data in
360 terms of both duration and magnitude (**Figure 7A**). Furthermore, simulations predict large differences in
361 peripheral tissue 3BNC117 amounts based on each mouse strain (**Figure 7B**). Interestingly, by decreasing
362 the abundance of Fc γ R in NSG mice equal to the population value for BL6 mice or removing the effects of
363 ADA from BL6 mice ($T_{max} = 0$), predictions from these strains become more consistent with human data
364 (**Figure 7C-D**). Altogether, these results demonstrate that analysis of PK data collected in the NSG and
365 BL6 mouse strains, particularly regarding the clinical translatability of data, must consider mechanistic
366 differences influencing mAb PK.

367 **Discussion**

368 In this work, we generated a detailed dataset of 3BNC117 PK after bolus i.v., s.c., and i.p. injection in four
369 strains of mice to investigate the role of immune system composition in mAb PK. Our data demonstrates
370 that mouse strain significantly influences the PK of 3BNC117, with the fully immunocompetent C57BL6
371 and severely immunodeficient NSG strains exhibiting rapid clearance compared to other strains. To
372 investigate the mechanisms of these differences, we developed an mPBPK model incorporating Fc γ R
373 binding and internalization and empirical terms representing the formation of ADA. By fitting our model

374 to the collected data and ensuring that trends in the literature are replicated, we demonstrated that the
375 mechanisms incorporated into our model are biologically feasible. We next estimated the corresponding
376 human PK profile of 3BNC117 based on each mouse strain. Comparing the predicted profiles to clinical
377 trial data in HIV-negative patients, we demonstrated that the PK parameters obtained from BL6 and NSG
378 mice lead to inaccurate predictions of human PK. Overall, our findings demonstrate that analysis of PK
379 data obtained from BL6 or NSG mice must consider the differences in mechanisms exhibited by these
380 strains, especially when assessing translatability of data.

381 Our conclusions regarding the NSG strain are primarily based on model-driven hypotheses; however, we
382 believe that our predictions are consistent with previous investigations in the literature and are biologically
383 feasible. The influence of Fc γ R binding on the PK of mAbs in NSG mice has been previously characterized
384 and shown to be the primary driver of rapid clearance in NSG mice. Sharma et al. [26] previously
385 demonstrated through the use of in vivo imaging that several cancer-targeted mAbs accumulate in the
386 spleen, liver, and bone marrow in NOD SCID and NSG mice in an Fc-binding dependent manner. In a
387 similar study, Li et al. [28] evaluated the PK of several mAbs and antibody-drug conjugates and found that
388 NSG mice exhibited significantly faster clearance than other strains. Interestingly, preventing binding
389 between the biologic and Fc γ R in NSG mice led to normal PK profiles. These trends were also reported in
390 a separate publication by Oldham and colleagues [27]. Our results complement these findings by illustrating
391 the effects of mouse strain on alternative administration routes, i.e., s.c. and i.p., and by characterizing these
392 trends with mathematical modeling with a specific emphasis on translatability.

393 Preclinical characterization of mAbs or other biologics is often evaluated in immunocompromised mouse
394 models to control for xenogeneic responses to the therapeutic being delivered. During these experiments,
395 selecting a mouse model that will exhibit translatable PK is critical. By estimating strain-specific PK
396 parameters with our mPBPK model, we approximated the translatability of each mouse model through
397 allometric scaling to predict human model parameters based on each strain. We selected 3BNC117 for this
398 study because the variable region of the antibody does not bind any targets in mice, and clinical trial data

399 is available in HIV- patients such that target binding is also absent [32]. Therefore, dosing of 3BNC117 in
400 both mice and HIV- humans results in PK profiles unaffected by mAb target binding, or target-mediated
401 drug disposition (TMDD) [59]. Simulated PK profiles using allometrically scaled human PK parameters
402 from each strain demonstrate that NSG- and BL6-scaled predictions are far different from observed clinical
403 trial data when differences in mechanism are not considered [32]. Conversely, RAG2- and BCD-scaled
404 predictions were consistent with human data. Overall, these results demonstrate that the assessment
405 translatability of PK data collected in NSG or BL6 mice must consider mechanistic differences, specifically,
406 the abnormal biodistribution due to increased FcγR abundance in peripheral tissues of NSG mice and the
407 immunogenic response to human IgG in BL6 mice. BCD and RAG2 mice were found to exhibit more easily
408 translatable PK data, suggesting that these strains may be better suited for preclinical study of mAb PK due
409 to ease of analysis.

410 Our findings are particularly important regarding the preclinical characterization of drug delivery systems
411 for the controlled release of mAbs and other large biologics, including drug delivery devices and gene
412 therapies. The development of these technologies is of great interest today because of their ability to
413 maintain therapeutic drug concentrations at target tissues and safe concentrations in circulation.
414 Accordingly, these technologies are in development for the treatment of a variety of diseases, including
415 cancer [15,16,60–62], macular degeneration [17,63,64], inflammatory disease [64,65], and HIV [66,67]. In
416 all these cases, preclinical characterization of the delivered therapeutic's PK is essential.
417 Immunocompromised mouse models are often selected for these experiments to allow study of therapeutic
418 PK in the absence of any xenogeneic responses against the drug or device itself. However, selecting a small
419 animal model that exhibits translatable PK is critical to streamline preclinical experimentation. An ideal
420 KO model for preclinical assessment of PK is sufficiently immunocompromised to mitigate the ADA or
421 FBR responses but still exhibits clinically translatable PK. By characterizing the effects of immune KO on
422 3BNC117 in detail, we emphasize the importance of selecting an appropriate mouse model and demonstrate
423 that mechanistic differences between mouse strains must be considered when assessing translatability.

424 **Author Contributions**

425 Jonathon DeBonis: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft,
426 Visualization. Anthony Davis: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal Analysis,
427 Investigation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization. Zeshi Wang: Investigation. Cody Fell:
428 Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing. Michael Diehl: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing
429 – Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. Oleg Igoshin: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing –
430 Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. Omid Veischi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review
431 & Editing, Funding acquisition.

432 **Acknowledgements**

433 This work was supported by the Gates Foundation (INV-051204) and by Welch Foundation Award C-
434 1995 (to OAI). Parameter estimation was performed using the Big-Data Private-Cloud
435 Research Cyberinfrastructure MRI-award funded by NSF under grant CNS-1338099 and by Rice
436 University's Center for Research Computing (CRC). This material is based upon work supported by the
437 National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship Program awarded to Anthony Davis. Any
438 opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the
439 authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation. The 3BNC117
440 protein was provided by the CAVD Protein Production Central Services Facility at the Duke Human
441 Vaccine Institute (DHVI). The CAVD Protein Production Facility is supported by a Collaboration for
442 AIDS Vaccine Discovery grant (INV-045468) from the Gates Foundation.

443 **Conflicts of Interest**

444 There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

445 **Supplementary Information**

446 Supplementary information to this article can be found in the attached PDF file “Supplementary
447 Information.pdf”. Calculated NCA parameters for each mouse are located in the attached spreadsheet
448 “Supplementary Data 1.xlsx” and PK data in format required for parameter estimation is located in
449 “Supplementary Data 2.xlsx”. R scripts used for model simulation can be found at
450 https://github.com/jcd111/3BNC117_mPBPK_Model.

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